

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

Deliverable 3.1 Outreach programmes

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1. INTRODUCTION

This report is an overview of the outreach activities organised by the ZEP/IWG9 secretariat between September 2023 and October 2024, to disseminate knowledge and recommendations from the Networks and Temporary Working Groups to broader stakeholders. A previous version of this deliverable was delivered to CINEA in November 2023.

There are already numerous outreach activities baked into the platform. For instance, in 2023 ZEP played a central role in the CCUS Forum as co-chair of the working group on CO₂ infrastructure, co-chair of the working group vision, and coordinator of the expert group on CO₂ specifications. ZEP has also given clear input to the co-chairs of the working group on industrial partnerships, highlighting that ZEP would be the best basis for the proposed Industrial Partnership. This central role in three crucial workstreams of the Forum has led to constant contacts and engagement with DG ENER on key policy files.

ZEP is also represented at the expert group on CDR and the Innovation Fund expert group. This allows for direct engagement with EC officials working on the Innovation Fund and the CDR framework.

Through its networks and working groups, the ZEP engages with EU policymakers on a permanent basis through its different workstreams. EC officials typically provide updates and presentations on key policy files during ZEP meetings, which allow members to engage with them on CCS and CCU.

The Network Technology and Network Policy & Economics meet 3-4 times a year and create a space for interventions by and engagement with EC officials from DG CLIMA, DG ENER, and DG RTD. The working groups under these two Networks meet more frequently and provide the same engagement space.

2. OUTREACH PROGRAMMES TOWARD EU AND NATIONAL OFFICIALS

2023-2024 is an extremely busy period for EU and national officials working on CCUS (policy files included the Industrial Carbon Management Strategy, the Austrian Carbon Management Strategy, the French Carbon Management Strategy, the key elements of the German Carbon Management Strategy, and the EU regulation Net-Zero Industry Act). The ZEP secretariat sent reports and papers to EU and national organisms directly via email. Mindful of their limited availability, the secretariat only set up dedicated meetings at the request of these public officials.

ZEP prepared an outreach programme for 2023 that was approved by the Advisory Council in December 2022. *See work programme 2023 under Annex A.*

ZEP prepared an outreach programme for 2024 that was approved by the Advisory Council in December 2023. *See work programme 2024 under Annex A.*

ZEP prepared an advocacy plan for 2024 that was presented at the Advisory Council in June 2024. *See advocacy strategy 2024 under Annex A.*

3. MEETINGS WITH PUBLIC OFFICIALS

Clean Transition Dialogue

ZEP Secretary General Joop Hazenberg gave an intervention at the Clean Transition Dialogue on 22 February 2024. The Clean Transition Dialogues are direct engagements between the European Commission and industry to support the deployment of energy infrastructure. Joop Hazenberg highlighted the critical importance of ICM deployment via:

- a strong and stable EU ETS price to guarantee market stability;
- a stronger Innovation Fund to kick-start critical investments;
- supportive national frameworks, like the Dutch SDE+++ , driving industrial decarbonisation forward; and
- a reinforced Connecting Europe Facility for rolling out CO₂ networks.

More information on ZEP's engagement can be found under the European Commission's news item and ZEP's LinkedIn publication (link to the [news item](#) and [publication](#)).

Meeting with EC Director for Green Transition and Energy System Integration

ZEP Chair Eve Tamme and ZEP Secretary General Joop Hazenberg met with Catharina Sikow-Magny, European Commission Director for Green Transition and Energy System Integration at the Directorate-General for Energy, on 11 September 2023 at the Directorate-General's offices in Brussels. Discussions with Ms Sikow-Magny focused on the Industrial Carbon Management Strategy under preparation, the possible future regulatory framework on CO₂ transport infrastructure, and the PCI/PMI selection process. Discussions also revolved around the possibility for ZEP to support future work around ICM.

Meeting with Cabinet of Commissioner of DG CLIMA

In March 2024, ZEP Secretary General Joop Hazenberg and ZEP Chair, Eve Tamme, together with members of the ZEP met with Daniel Mes from DG CLIMA Commissioner, Wopke Hoekstra's cabinet, to discuss the

industrial carbon management strategy, accelerating the development of lead markets for industrial products and the importance of scaling up CCS and CCU in the next Commission.

Discussion on NZIA Strategic Components

ZEP Secretary General Eadhard Pernot, along with ZEP Member Representatives from Bellona, MHI and ExxonMobil, met with DG-ENER at the DG-GROW offices to discuss the NZIA Delegated Act on Strategically Used Components on 13 September 2024. The meeting focused on manufacturing for CCS and the criteria used to determine the Delegated Act on Primarily Used Components list. The EC requested any feedback to be provided by mid-October 2024, to publish the Delegated Act in March 2025.

The ZEP Secretariat gathered feedback from members, and provided feedback to the EC on:

- Solvents and sorbents
- CO₂ purification and liquefaction equipment
- CO₂ Compressors
- CO₂ well drilling equipment
- CO₂ injection wellhead

The document provided can be found in Annex A.

Meetings with National Public Officials

The EU regulation Net-Zero Industry Act is one of the most important pieces of legislation for deploying CCUS in Europe. This regulation creates, among others, a minimum EU injection capacity objective of 50 million tonnes of CO₂ per year. Article 23 of this regulation creates a mandatory contribution for oil and gas producers to this objective.

Due to the importance of this Article, the Secretariat and the Policy & Economics Committee co-chair held two separate online meetings with German and French representatives to inform them about ZEP's position on the Net-Zero Industry Act and to understand the position of these two Member States regarding this legislative file.

IWG9 countries meeting

This meeting gathered IWG9 country representatives on 1 March 2024 from 10:00 to 11:00 (CET). The objective of this meeting was to discuss the process of updating the CCUS R&I targets and activities. The second agenda item focused on 'Policy developments' and aimed to provide a policy update to the country representatives to ensure that the revision process is aligned with recent policy developments including the impact assessment of the 2040 EU climate target proposed by the European Commission.

IWG9 country representatives received a briefing on the following:

- New policy targets for CCS/CCU under the Net-Zero Industry Act and the Industrial Carbon Management Strategy; and
- The creation of the SET Plan Steering Group under the EU regulation Net-Zero Industry Act.

The meeting agenda and presentation can be found under Annex A.

SET Plan Steering Group

The secretariat briefed the members of the SET Plan Steering Group during a dedicated session on 14 December 2023. The briefing focused on the work done by ZEP and the IWG9, and the current project and policy developments for CCUS.

The presentation can be found under Annex A

ZEP Projects Network

The Zero Emissions Platform with Porthos organised the first edition of the Projects Network in Rotterdam on 24 and 25 January 2024. The meeting gathered over 120 delegates from across 17 European countries. Sessions were organised to provide feedback and learning from the Porthos project to public officials and other CCS project developers and managers. The key takeaways of the sessions were noted down by participants on flip charts and shared with participants after the meeting. The recommendations from this first edition are currently under review and will be shared with policymakers.

The Projects Network is intended to provide on-the-ground recommendations from projects to the Government Group to facilitate the deployment of projects and address identified on-the-ground problems that should be resolved by policymakers.

A government representative from Germany attended the first edition in Rotterdam and was briefed on the technical and commercial learnings from the Porthos project. This representative gave very positive feedback on the functioning of the Projects Network during the Government Group meeting in March 2024.

More information can be found under the dedicated ZEP webpage and the LinkedIn publication (link to the [webpage](#) and [publication](#)).

MEP site visit: Porthos and Aramis projects

The ZEP Secretariat coordinated a site visit to the Porthos and Aramis projects for Renew MEPs Pascal Canfin and Jeannette Baljeu on 30 October 2024. The visit aimed to obtain insights into how the projects will operate and contribute to industrial decarbonisation, into how CO₂ storage and transport processes work on a technical level, and exchange with project developers on best practices and hurdles they have experiences in developing both projects.

4. WEBINARS ATTENDED BY PUBLIC OFFICIALS

‘Scaling up storage: mapping Europe’s CO₂ storage sites’

This webinar took place on 24 May 2024 on Microsoft Teams. It is the most attended meeting organised by ZEP under the grant period. 355 participants attended this webinar that aimed at “ensuring accurate communication about CO₂ storage capacity estimates and the status of ongoing and planned storage projects, crucial for the timely creation of the EU CO₂ storage atlas”. The targeted audience was EU and national officials with two objectives:

- communicating to EU and national public officials the difference between theoretical and available storage capacity; and
- underlining the efforts required to develop the storage sites necessary to meet the 2030 injection capacity objective under the EU regulation Net-Zero Industry Act.

29 European public officials attended this webinar.

More information on the webinar can be found on the ZEP website (link to the [dedicated webpage](#)). A full recording of the webinar is available on YouTube (link to the [video](#)).

‘Charting the course for CCS: Launch of the CO₂ transport by ship report’

This webinar took place on 9 January 2023 on Zoom. Approximately 250 participants attended this webinar, the second most attended meeting under the grant period. This webinar aimed to communicate to policymakers the importance of supportive policies for shipping as a critical element of the CCS supply chain.

Johanna Fiksdahl, policy officer at the European Commission Directorate-General for Energy, took part in the panel discussion and Q&A.

More information on ZEP’s engagement can be found under ZEP’s LinkedIn publication (link to the [news item](#) and [publication](#)). A screenshot of the publication can also be found below.

5. PUBLISHED BRIEFINGS AND IWG9 PLENARIES/ADVISORY COUNCILS PRE-READS

The secretariat produces information on CCUS policy developments. This information includes IWG9 Plenaries/Advisory Councils pre-reads for attendees, including EU and national public officials. Government Group representatives are on the distribution list and receive these pre-reads.

The secretariat also produces briefings published on the website. Those are available to the public, including EU and public officials. Recently published briefings include the following:

- [ZEP Briefing – 2040 EU Climate Target](#) published on 12 February 2024
- [ZEP Briefing – Industrial Carbon Management Strategy](#) published on 12 February 2024
- [ZEP Briefing – ESABCC post-2030 climate policy recommendations](#) published on 31 January 2024

ANNEX A: OUTREACH PROGRAMMES, ADVOCACY PLANS, AGENDAS AND MINUTES

Draft ZEP and IWG9 work programme for 2023

The draft joint ZEP and IWG9 work programme, with both common areas and areas that are specific for ZEP and IWG9 respectively, was presented for guidance at the ZEP AC and IWG9 Plenary in September. It has since been discussed with the Networks, Government group, the External Relations Group (ERG) and the Communication Group, resulting in some adjustments. Terms of References (ToR) for the workstreams highlighted in the work programme will, as usual, be drafted for approval. For the immediately upcoming workstreams, draft ToRs have been prepared and discussed with Networks, and are presented for approval under item 4, Network updates, in today's agenda.

The work programme is a living document based on the EU (and member state) policy agenda with a focus on CCS and CCU, and directly linked to the coordinated ZEP and IWG9 governance structure: the Networks and TWGs, the ERG and Communication Group, and the Government Group.

Focus areas on overarching level

- Coordination and close cooperation between ZEP and the IWG9, to continue providing strong support and input to the CCUS SET-Plan (IWG9) activities – necessary to reach Europe's ambitious 2030 climate goals – and a high level of coordination with other European and global programmes. A review of the coordination and governance structure will also be in the plans.

- The CCUS Forum is the key vehicle for the EC regarding the development of CCUS in Europe. ZEP is engaged in the Forum working groups (WG) as co-chair of two of the three WGs and an active member in the third. It is crucial to continue the strong engagement in this work – that includes two of ZEP's key: an EU strategy for CCS and CCU, and a regulatory framework for CO2 transport infrastructure.
- As more and more CCS/CCU projects are becoming market-ready, there is a need to intensify the support for these projects, cooperate closely and monitor their development.

Delivering on the day-to-day work

Network Policy & Economics (NWPE)

The Network and the TWG Policy & Funding remains the main point of contact for the preparation of responses to consultations and other input to the EC. Focus areas for the NWPE:

- The CCUS Forum and the ongoing and planned working groups: For the consultation on the 2023 EC Communication, CO₂ infrastructure, Industrial partnership, and Public awareness. Providing support to the Forum work, with the special aim of enabling an EU strategy for CCS and CCU and the proposed regulatory framework for CO₂ transport infrastructure, will be of key importance to maintain the positive momentum and drive implementation.
- The two EC studies – the technical study on CO₂ transport infrastructure and the study on regulatory issues on CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure. The upcoming revision of the National Energy and Climate Plans (NECP).
- Provide insights on EU and national support instruments for CCUS R&I and deployment and how they interact (in cooperation with the Network Technology (NWT)).
- The policy instruments under the ‘Fit for 55 package’, with a focus on the EU ETS, the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism, the Innovation Fund, and the Renewable Energy Directive.
- The upcoming work on a revision of the Monitoring and Reporting Regulation.
- Follow and contribute to the revision of the CO₂ Storage Directive Guidance Documents ([link](#)). The NWT will focus on technical aspects and the NWPE will support on regulatory and funding aspects.
- CO₂ transport by ship (*see draft ToR under agenda item 4*), follow-up from the first WG on CO₂ transport by ship. The aim is to investigate the scope and trade routes for CO₂ ship transport, follow up on interoperability and the work done by ISO, IMO, and SIGTTO, address existing barriers to commercialisation, and identify possible work needed for a Europe-wide CO₂ storage market.

Network Technology (NWT)

The Network will continue its very active work programme, engaging experts from members and observers on technical aspects regarding deployment of CCS and CCU. Focus areas for the NWT:

- Carbon Dioxide Removals (CDR) – The TWG CDR will continue to follow and give input to the ongoing international work of Mission Innovation on CDR. Moreover, it will follow up on the Communication on Sustainable Carbon Cycles – notably, the recently adopted EC proposal on a certification framework for carbon removals, incentive schemes, the development of voluntary carbon markets, accounting, standards and methodologies, including compliance with article 6 of the Paris Agreement. The TWG will be the central focus for ZEP’s work on CDR and will be supported by the NWPE (*see ToR for extended work under agenda item 4*).

- Recommendations on CCUS R&I priorities for the Horizon Europe work programme.
- Progress review and recommendations on the key IWG9 R&I activities. The plan is to have six reports updating R&I activities over the coming three years, starting with a report focused on CO₂ transport infrastructure and PCIs (2023). For 2024 and 2025 there will be reports on Capture, Storage, Utilisation, Commercial-scale CCS and Linking EU and national strategies and plans on CCS and CCU. These reports will follow up and be based on the eight R&I activities reports prepared by the IWG9.
- Analysis of the implications that the energy crisis – specifically the reduced access to energy – will have on the different CCS and CCU technologies (and thus the transition towards net-zero).
- Analysis of the risks involved in the CCUS supply chain – including materials, technology, and expertise (*see draft ToR under agenda item 4*).
- Follow and provide input on the EC/JRC technical study on optimal CO₂ networks.
- Provide guidance and input to the CCUS Forum Working Group on CO₂ infrastructure, regarding CO₂ specifications in the context of an integrated European CO₂ transport and storage network. The aim is to build a common understanding on CO₂ specifications along the value chain. The focus will be on the need for standards and the framework under which such these could be developed. How this work will be set up and undertaken will be discussed with the Network Technology co-chairs.
- Follow and contribute to the revision of the CO₂ Storage Directive Guidance Documents ([link](#)). The NWT will focus on technical aspects and the NWPE will support on regulatory and funding aspects.
- The NWT will support the TWG on CO₂ transport by ship regarding objective 1 and 2 of the appended (*see draft ToR under agenda item 4*).

New Network Projects (*depending on other EU grants*)

Creation of this Network in the ZEP structure will depend on the extent to which other EU grants cover this topic. Focus areas for this Network:

- *Supporting market-ready projects from a policy, funding and technological point of view*
- *Addressing existing barriers*
- *Improving public perception, and*
- *Enabling knowledge sharing.*

External Relations Group (ERG)

For the areas of specific interest for ZEP – highlighted above – the ERG will guide communications and outreach activities. Given the many ongoing EU policy initiatives

and legislative processes, the initial focus of communications for end-2022 and 2023 will be to secure meetings with policymakers and provide input to EU policy initiatives. In parallel, the ERG will guide the execution – on behalf of the AC – of the communications and dissemination activities connected to the ZEP reports, hosting events and webinars, and communicating through social media and the newsletter. The ZEP Communications Group will play an important role here, as a direct channel to the wider group of members for coordination and information exchange on messages and activities.

Government Group

With several countries preparing national strategies for CCUS and an increasing number of ongoing and planned CCUS projects across Europe, the ZEP Government Group – where the interest from member states and permanent representations is growing – will be crucial in the coordination between EU and national strategies, policies, and funding opportunities.

Draft ZEP and IWG9 Work Programme 2024

Version 5 December 2023

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1. Introduction

2024 will be an important year for the carbon capture and storage (CCS) community in Europe. The spade will go into the ground for the first commercial CCS site in the EU (Porthos in the Netherlands), Northern Lights will become the first project to deliver cross-border CO₂ transport and storage, the European Commission launches the long-awaited Industrial Carbon Management Strategy, there are elections for the European Parliament and Member States need to review their National Energy and Climate Plans. After many lost years, CCS seems to finally be moving from development to deployment as a key technology to drive the decarbonisation of Europe's hard-to-abate sectors.

The Zero Emissions Platform (ZEP) and the Implementation Working Group 9 of the SET-Plan (IWG9) are at the forefront of CCS policy making, on the one hand as the trusted advisors to the EU and as Member States working collectively to achieve Europe's climate goals – notably on the decarbonisation of the energy intensive industries. In this document, we provide an outline of our main activities for 2024.

The governance structures of ZEP and IWG9 are largely merged, and their secretariat is funded by a single Horizon Europe grant (running from July 2022 to June 2025), hence the choice for a joint work programme. We will also include those activities that are *de facto* funded by the members of ZEP, resulting in extra bandwidth for a programme that goes beyond the deliverables set out in the Horizon Europe grant agreement. For the sake of clarity, those deliverables for 2024 will be spelt out in detail below.

The work programme should be considered as a living and reference document, especially for those active in the various working groups as well as for the secretariat and the organisations executing the grant. It could also be changed depending on the outcome of the ZEP restructuring – a process underway now and should be implemented in 2024. As ZEP aims to strengthen its advocacy and communications workstream, this could alter the goals and deliverables of this work programme. Hence, a certain amount of flexibility and agility should be taken into account.

2. Main policy developments in 2024

Before we dive into the work streams, let's zoom out and look at the main CCS and CCU related policy developments that we expect to happen in 2024.

In Q1 2024, the European Commission is expected to publish a proposal for an EU 2040 climate target. ZEP expects the proposal to provide further clarity on the role of CCS and CCU in contributing to the EU's climate targets, seeks to inform the co-decision process on the 2040 target and contribute to the upcoming legislative processes where existing EU legislation will be aligned with the 2040 target.

The 2040 climate target proposal will be complemented by an **Industrial Carbon Management Strategy (ICMS)**. The ICMS will assess what role CCS and CCU technologies can play in reducing and removing emissions in the EU economy until 2050, as well as what measures are needed to scale them up, including in the deployment of EU-wide CO₂ transport and storage infrastructures. This strategy will be crucial to set out the European Commission's vision on the role of CCS in Europe and what policy measures are needed to achieve this vision. The new Commission, expected to start at the end of 2024, is expected to propose policy initiatives supporting CCS.

- ZEP will continue to advocate for a strong ICMS in line with ZEP's recommendations on the strategy, as specified in [the contribution](#) to the ICMS consultation of 2023.
- If a consultation is opened following the publication of the strategy, ZEP will respond to the consultation.
- ZEP is ready to engage and support the Commission in the potential deliverables or initiatives proposed in the ICMS, provided that these align and enhance ZEP's impact in the deployment of CCS and CCU technologies

A landmark piece of legislation for CCS will undoubtedly be the **Net Zero Industry Act**, proposed by the Commission in early 2023. This proposal for a regulation will be under negotiation between the EU institutions (trilogues) in late 2023/early 2024. The two key elements in the NZIA are the 50Mt CO₂ annual injection capacity target for the EU in 2030 and its Article 18. Together with other stakeholders, the ZEP published [an open letter](#) in July 2023 calling for an implementable and pragmatic Net Zero Industry Act Article 18.

- ZEP will continue its support for the NZIA as it will spur the deployment of CCS in Europe. The NZIA should be approved before the **2024 European Parliament** elections. ZEP will insist on this timeline in its contact with policymakers.
- ZEP will make recommendations to the three institutions during the trilogues regarding the provisions best placed to support CCS deployment in Europe.

The European Parliament elections will take place from 6 to 9 June 2024. A new European Parliament entails a new European Commission. Both institutions will play a critical role in translating the 2040 climate targets into the right political and regulatory framework. As CCS will play an important role in achieving these climate targets, the Zero Emissions Platform seeks a (pro)active dialogue with the Commission and the Parliament, pushing for an

ambitious CCS agenda in the next EU legislative cycle. The ICMS is an obvious lever for such an agenda, but more political pressure will be needed.

- ZEP will further develop its advocacy and communications strategy and undertake efforts to have CCS represented in programmes of the main European political parties and the new European Commission's policy agenda.
- ZEP will engage with EU policymakers ahead of the elections to highlight the importance of CCS and CCU deployment and the need to develop EU and national funding programmes that fit the requirements to reach climate neutrality by 2050.

On the national level, EU member states are required to send updated **National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs)** to the Commission. The Guidance to Member States encourages national governments to include CCS provisions¹. Several Member States are in the process of developing their own carbon management strategies, such as Germany and France, while others are only beginning to explore CCS strategies (such as Spain).

- Together with other stakeholders, ZEP will analyse the updated NECPs and provide feedback on those NECPs where policies are insufficient and/or lacking.
- Pending internal capacity, ZEP will work with national governments to support them in their development of national carbon management strategies.

The European Commission published the Strategic Technologies for Europe Platform (STEP) proposal for a regulation at the end of June 2023 to support investments in critical technologies, such as CCS and CCU. An agreement on this proposal could take place in Q1 2024.

- ZEP will monitor the legislative progress of the STEP proposal and support the increase in the Innovation Fund and Horizon Europe programmes.
- ZEP will support the STEP proposal and highlight the need to develop EU and national funding programmes and to incentivise investments in line with the funding required for CCS to reach the 2040 and 2050 climate targets.

CCUS Forum

ZEP is one of the co-chairs of the CCUS Forum working group on CO₂ infrastructure and has contributed to several CCUS Forum working groups.

- ZEP will support the preparation of the 2024 plenary.
- ZEP will support and contribute to the potential future work of the CCUS Forum working group on CO₂ infrastructure and the CCUS Forum expert group on CO₂ specifications.

CDR

The European Commission published a proposal for a regulation on an EU certification for carbon removals in November 2022. Trilogues on the proposal have started start in Q4 2023 and policymakers are committed to reach an agreement before the European Parliament

¹ [Guidance to Member States for updated NECPs 2021-2030](#), European Commission.

recesses in March 2024. Following the adoption of the regulation, the European Commission, in collaboration with a dedicated expert group, will work on the preparation of a methodologies for carbon dioxide removals (CDR) certification framework throughout 2024.

- ZEP will closely monitor the progress of the proposal and will make policy recommendations, where useful.
- ZEP will contribute to the preparation of a CDR methodologies via its representative in the Expert Group, Kristin Jordal, and by responding to future potential calls for inputs.

ZEP will also follow the adoption of delegated acts amending the EU ETS Monitoring and Reporting Regulation and relevant for CCS and CCU deployment.

Finally, ZEP will closely monitor developments related to key EU funding programmes, including the Connecting Europe Facility, the Innovation Fund, Horizon Europe, and LIFE.

3. ZEP and IWG9 working groups

Several hundreds of CCS experts meet regularly in meetings that the secretariat organises – mostly in the context of ZEP but also in combined sessions with IWG9 delegates. The main meetings continue to be the **Advisory Council** which gathers four times per year and is attended by ZEP members, the IWG9 constituency but also by interested parties that are not formally connected to either organisation. In June 2024, the Advisory Council will include a meeting of the **ZEP Communications ASBL** that gathers once a year. (This is the Belgian non-profit organisation with a membership structure that sponsors the ZEP secretariat and additional activities, on top of the EU grant)

Depending on political and economic developments, these are the most important work items per forum. The ZEP secretariat runs several bodies where members meet, both of the ZEP and of IWG9: Committees, Temporary Working Groups (which fall under Committees), and a new Projects Network. It also provides the secretariat for the ZEP Government Group, which consists of representatives of around twenty European governments.

Policy & Economics Committee
Paragraph to follow later

Technology Committee

The Technology Committee (TC) will organise four meetings in 2024; the meeting taking place in or close to September will be an in-person meeting in Brussels; the other three will be virtual meetings.

Mission Innovation CDR. TC supports the EC in their participation in Mission Innovation on CDR. This has been an ongoing activity in 2023 and will be continued in 2024. The TWG CDR will meet regularly, guided by activities in the MI CDR. The work in the Removals Expert Group is part of this activity.

One report is currently in the pipeline. The TWG will continue their work and finalise their reports in 2024. The TWG CCS supply chain has been suspended. Remaining work includes:

- **Flexible power with CCS** (tbc, co-leads Arthur Heberle, Robert de Kler)

Topics for approval by the AC:

1. Transport cost: recent publications suggest that transport costs for landlocked emitters may reach €200/t, for the CO₂ to reach a coastline by rail and/or pipeline. A ZEP paper could be written on this topic, to highlight the issues and suggest ways forward (e.g., stressing the need for onshore storage). Just as with the aforementioned two reports, there is a capacity issue within the secretariat

2. CO₂ specifications: way forward. Recent development in the knowledge of the effects of and behaviour of impurities in CO₂ streams have led to strict specifications. This leads to increasing cost of purification for emitters, potentially making CCS unaffordable. A two-pipe solution to handle captured CO₂ from different capture technologies has also been suggested. The CCUS Forum expert group that produced the report for the CCUS-Forum could be invited to reflect on these issues.

Projects Network

In 2023 ZEP created the Projects Network that will support the many ongoing and planned CCS and CCU projects in Europe. The Network should also address existing barriers and help de-risking investments, improve public perception of CCS, and enable real project-to-project knowledge sharing. By introducing this network, ZEP establishes an important tool to efficiently support projects and, at the same time, actively help the EC and European governments regarding necessary policy/regulation, funding and actions linked to public perception.

The Projects Network is in development and will be launched officially at the Porthos site in Rotterdam, 24-25 January 2024. For the rest of the year, one or two more of such events could be organised in order to facilitate the exchange of knowledge among project developers and keep the momentum.

At the CCUS Forum 2023, the European Commission unveiled plans to launch their own industrial carbon management knowledge sharing network where participation will be mandatory for projects that have received EU funding, and voluntary and encouraged for others. Once the ICMS has been published and further details are known, ZEP will explore the options of informing this new initiative via its own Projects Network experience to date and if dedicated funding is available, consider bidding to provide the secretariat for the Commission's network, streamlining the two initiatives into one.

The current ZEP Project Network does not have dedicated funding source, has been having challenges in confirming co-chairs and the detailed governance structure is yet to be established. However, if the future entails joining forces with the European Commission's network, these challenges would be addressed.

External Relations Committee

The External Relations Group plays a crucial role in providing strategic guidance to ZEP's external communications activities, as well as in promoting ZEP's mission and identity across its wide network of stakeholders. The ERG co-chairs also contribute to the development of external engagements with policymakers and are able to represent ZEP at these meetings.

Effective coordination between ERG and ACEC as well as the other committees is important to ensure the external facing activities are timely, focussed and effective.

Three main pillars identified:

- 1) Organisational (internal)
 - Work on clear Terms of Reference and Governance for ERG in its new configuration
 - Ensure that interaction /coordination with the other ZEP Committees is clearly organised, efficient, and effective (e.g. with ACEC, Policy & Economics, Government, etc)
- 2) External – socialisation of Policy /Technical work of ZEP Committees with relevant stakeholders

- Develop and tailor an advocacy and communication plan based on the work program of the ZEP Committees by its January 2023 meeting – the plan needs to be fit for purpose and not too generic
 - Ensure a throughout review of the communication tools and practices (stakeholder mapping, messaging, use of social media, website, etc) to ensure an effective implementation of the external relations and communication program
- 3) External: Assess potential role of ZEP in the area of public acceptance:
- Education (for example in the Parliament after elections, with local authorities in Member states, in schools and universities)
 - Support (including to authorities / local authorities) with communication materials, events, etc to reach the general public

As highlighted in the introduction, the work programme covers activities funded by the Horizon Europe grant and those funded by member sponsorships to ZEP-Communications ABSL. Following from “additional work programme”, adopted by ZEP for 2023 for activities funded by member sponsorships, the 2024 work programme covers all both grant- and member-funded activities. In 2023, the focus of activities funded by member sponsorships was advocacy, communications, events and visibility. 2024 work programme continues this approach, and these activities are likely to overwhelmingly fit under the External Relation Committee’s activities:

- Establishing an advocacy and communications implementation plan with clear KPIs
 - Establishing specific goals for engaging with policymakers on CCS-related policy files
 - Establishing renewed brand voice and messages for ZEP that is used uniformly in all communication – what the organisation does, its principles, its value proposition for members
 - Increase ZEP visibility across social media platforms
 - Explore rebranding ZEP and revamping ZEP website
 - Raising the profile of CCS as a climate technology
- Organising annual ZEP CCS Conference in April 2024

4. Research and Innovation

From [SETIS](#):

- *The European Strategic Energy Technology Plan (SET Plan) is a key stepping stone to boost the transition towards a climate-neutral energy system through the development of low-carbon technologies in a fast and competitive way.*
- *The SET Plan was established in 2007 and since the creation of the energy union in 2015, it became one of the main instruments of the energy union's 5th pillar on research innovation and competitiveness.*
- *By improving new technologies and bringing down their costs through coordinated national research efforts, the SET Plan helps promote cooperation among EU countries, companies and research institutions. It does so by helping to coordinate national research and innovation activities in developing low-carbon energy among EU countries and associated countries, as well as aligning national research and innovation programmes with its agenda.*

The [SET plan activities](#) are clustered into 10 actions for research and innovation, whereas CCUS is number 9 (thereby the number 9 in the SET Plan Implementation Working Group, IWG, for CCUS):

The [CCUS SET Plan Implementation Working Group \(IWG9\)](#) is chaired by the Netherlands, Norway and Zero Emissions Platform (ZEP) and established a few years ago ambitious 2030 targets and R&I activities. These are now ready for updating – and this work will be carried out in 2024.

The organisation of the SET plan work may be illustrated as follows:

Formal SET PLAN ACTORS

1. ETIPs: European Innovation and Technology Platforms
2. EERA: European Energy Research Alliance
3. Governments: National and EU COM

In addition to these formal bodies of the SET Plan on CCUS, it is important to engage widely in all corners of this triangle – ranging from industry, R&I and governments – for the impact of the SET Plan work to increase.

An important part of the ZEP/IWG9 work is to advance the research and innovation agenda of CC(U)S in Europe. Notably within the IWG9 context, European countries should be more involved and exchange their latest insights of R&I projects.

At the EU grant preceding the current one for the secretariat of IWG9, a clear research agenda was spelled out; below follows a similar structure to organise the ZEP/IWG9 in this respect. Notably, ZEP will support the realisation of the SET Plan Implementation Plan on CCS and CCU which has defined eight key R&I activities with ten linked targets to be met.

The secretariat will increase its engagement with European governments to find more CCS R&I contact points and add these to our distribution lists.

The R&I Activities included in the existing [SET Plan Implementation Plan for CCUS](#), and that need to be updated, are the following (in brackets are reference made to R&I targets to be explained in the following section):

- R&I Activity 1: Delivery of a whole chain CCS project operating in the power sector (target 1).
- R&I Activity 2: Delivery of regional CCS and CCU clusters, including feasibility for a European hydrogen infrastructure (targets 2 & 3 and 10).
- R&I Activity 3: EU Projects of Common Interest for CO₂ transport infrastructure (target 4).
- R&I Activity 4: Establish a European CO₂ Storage Atlas (target 5).
- R&I Activity 5: Unlocking European Storage capacity (target 7).
- R&I Activity 6: Developing next-generation CO₂ capture technologies (target 6).
- R&I Activity 7: CCU Action (targets 8 & 9).

- R&I Activity 8: Understanding and communicating the role of CCS and CCU in meeting European and national energy and climate change goals (target 10).

CCUS SET-PLAN 2030 TARGETS

50 Mtpa abated by CCS in 2030

How to do this:

In the period 2019-2022 a separate grant supported the work of the SETR Plan Implementation Working Group on CCUS, namely the [IMPACTS9 project](#), coordinated by CCSA. The secretariat work of the CCUS SET Plan targets was implemented in the following way:

With reference to the CCUS SET plan 2030 targets, the work in 2019-2022 was organised in five sub-groups below with the responsibility to follow up the Targets listed below each sub-group:

Target 1,2,3,4

Target 6

Target 5, 7

Target 8, 9

Target 10

In the following year the plan is to organise this work in stronger collaboration with existing structures in ZEP (especially Technology Committee) and EERA JP CCS. In practice this will be reported back to the ZEP AC/IWG) plenary meetings quarterly.

5. Deliverables of the Horizon Europe grant

As stipulated in the EU grant agreement, ZEP and IWG9 need to complete the following deliverables in 2024. It will be a priority for the ZEP secretariat and SINTEF to not delay any of the following deliverables.

Work Package 1: Delivery of the CCUS SET Plan Implementation Plan

D1.4 Review of the IWG9 R&I activities and targets

Deadline June 2024, lead SINTEF, input IWG9 needed

D1.6 Recommendations focusing on Social Sciences and Humanities expertise

Deadline July 2024, lead CCSA

Based on the work on CCS/CCU projects, enablers and hurdles for new CCS and CCU projects, provide recommendations focusing on Social Sciences and Humanities expertise.

Work Package 2: Coordination of Networks and Temporary Working Groups

D2.2 Annual progress reviews and recommendations on the 8 R&I activities

Deadline May 2024, lead SINTEF, input IWG9 needed

Provide recommendations on the steps required to deliver each of the eight key IWG9 Research and Innovation (R&I) activities – providing an annual review of progress and where applicable including recommendations.

D2.4 Report on key enablers and hurdles for CCS/CCU projects, focus on public perception

Deadline February 2024, lead CCSA

Develop report on key enablers and hurdles for European CCS/CCU projects, with a focus on public perception.

Work Package 3: Support outreach and external relations

D3.1 Outreach programmes and briefings with European institutions and Member States

Deadline November 2024, lead CCSA

Prepare outreach programmes, plan and hold briefings with officials from the European institutions and Member States on output and conclusions from the project's technical, policy, regulatory, and economic work.

D3.4 Present outputs and recommendations at SET Plan Steering Group events, other EC initiatives, etc.

Deadline August 2024, lead CCSA

Present outputs at SET Plan Steering Group events and provide recommendations to other European Commission initiatives – e.g. Innovation Fund Expert Group and the European Clean Hydrogen Alliance, the Clean Energy Transition Partnership, the High Level Group on Energy Intensive Industries – and other international initiatives, e.g. Mission Innovation and the Clean Energy Ministerial.

Work Package 4: Support to the Government Group

D4.1 Disseminate reports and recommendations to Member States

Deadline November 2024, lead CCSA

Disseminate reports and recommendations to Member State representatives.

D4.2 Input from national governments on the focus and outputs from the project

Deadline June 2024, lead CCSA

Input from national governments on the focus and development of reports and other outputs from the project.

D4.3 Support from national governments on delivery of the Implementation Plan

Deadline June 2024, lead CCSA

Support from national governments on delivery of the Implementation Plan.

Work Package 5: Management of the project

D5.1 Project Management Plan

Deadline June 2024, lead CCSA

Project Management Plan with a Gantt chart and a Work Breakdown Structure. (review)

Further contact

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Agenda Item 6: Update from the External Relations Committee – IWG9, for information and guidance

6.a. IPCEI draft letter – for information and approval

ZEP, together with representatives from the entire CCS/CCU value chain, has co-led an open letter emphasising support for an industrial carbon management IPCEI (Important Projects of Common European Interest), encompassing CO₂ capture, removal, utilisation, transport, and storage. Signatories to the letter called on Member States' representatives of the Joint Forum for IPCEI (JEF-IPCEI) to prioritise ICM in the upcoming technical meeting and to increase the JEF-IPCEI effectiveness to allow for the rapid decarbonisation of hard-to-abate sectors.

The draft letter (*see below*) has been reviewed and approved by the Working Group Policy and Funding and endorsed by the Advisory Council Executive Committee.

The letter will be published on 17 June on ZEP's communication channels and distributed to Member States representatives member of the JEF-IPCEI.

The Advisory Council is invited to approve the draft letter.

6.b. Advocacy strategy – for information and guidance

As part of ongoing efforts to enhance ZEP advocacy as the EU trusted advisor on ICM, the Secretariat has developed an advocacy strategy, with the aim to tackle the following actions for the year 2024-2025:

EU legislation

- Implementation of Existing Initiatives: Focusing on the Industrial Carbon Management Strategy, NZIA, CRCF, and the EU ETS Monitoring and Reporting Regulation.
- New Initiatives: Preparing for the 2040 climate target and CO₂ infrastructure regulation.

Policy papers on industrial carbon management

- Ongoing: Clean Industrial Products and Services, and CDR Certification.
- Future: Recommendations for a European Regulatory Framework for CO₂ transport, CO₂ specifications, and CO₂ injection capacity obligation – making the NZIA work for CCS.

Knowledge sharing activities

- Hosting webinars and discussions on flexible power with CCS, scaling up storage, public support for CCS, and just transition.

ZEP engagement

- Engaging with European institutions including regular meetings with the Commission.
- ZEP will be participating in the ICM Forum
- ZEP has recently joined the European Energy Forum as a member and will be participating in regular events hosted by the EEF in the European Parliament and will look to establish a strong rapport with MEPs through the EEF, particularly on the ITRE and ENVI Committees.
- Events are also planned in Autumn 2024 including a side-event at the ICM Forum and potentially an event in the European Parliament, as well as a multi-government exchange on CCS policy.
- The ZEP secretariat has also participated in various events this year as a speaker including the Danish CCUS Summit, while future engagements are planned, including with the Indonesian CCS Center in late-July.

Supporting CO2 project development

- Providing ongoing support for CCS projects in Europe through letters of support for ZEP members, building the ZEP Projects Network, and sharing insights from developers and agencies.
- The 2nd Projects Network is due to be hosted in Antwerp later this year, followed by two events each year going forward.

Communications

- Enhancing our social media presence, undertaking ZEP rebranding, and revamping the website.

Coalition building

- Expanding ZEP network of carbon capture advocates by collaborating with CCS Europe, the Global CCS Institute, CO2 GeoNet, and other stakeholders.

The AC is invited to provide guidance on the advocacy strategy.

6.c. ZEP Conference – for information and guidance

The ZEP Annual Conference will be held on December 5th, from 12 PM to 6 PM CET. The venue for the conference is SPARKS, conveniently located next to Brussels Central Station. An organisational task force has been established to support the content development for the conference. The first meeting of the task force is yet to be scheduled for the end of June. If you wish to be involved in the organisation of the conference, [please reach out to the Secretariat](#).

6.d. Report on public perception – for information and approval

ZEP will publish a report “Public Perception: key enablers and hurdles for CCS and CCU projects” which was written in the framework of the IWG9ZEP grant agreement. The report delineates a number of considerations for achieving positive public perception of CCS and CCU, as illustrated by case studies. The report concludes with the key enablers and hurdles for CCS and CCU with a focus on public perception and awareness. The insights of the report will be disseminated in a social media campaign. A webinar delving further into the topic of public perception of CCS and CCU will take place on 20 June on Teams.

More information and registrations are available on this [page](#).

The AC is invited to approve the report on public perception.

DRAFT

Input on Delegated Act on “primarily used components”

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Introduction

Zero Emissions Platform (ZEP) is the trusted advisor to the European Union on industrial carbon management. Our comprehensive technical work and policy advice builds on a broad, diverse member base, ranging from energy producers and industrial companies to infrastructure and equipment providers, environmental NGOs, academia, and trade unions. ZEP runs the European Technology and Innovation Platform (ETIP) under the European SET-Plan funded by the Horizon Europe grant and collaborates closely with the European Commission.

Our mission is to accelerate the deployment of industrial carbon management and the buildout of CO₂ infrastructure in Europe in line with the EU’s climate ambition.

The objective of this paper is to provide objective input to the Delegated Act under the Net Zero Industry Act (NZIA) on defining ‘primarily used components’ for net zero technologies. The components listed in this document are relevant specifically for the purposes of carbon capture and storage (CCS) projects.

Each component listed is critical to the process of capturing, transporting and storing CO₂ permanently in geological storage sites, as regulated under the Directive 2009/31/EC, commonly referred to as the “CCS Directive”.

1. Solvents and sorbents

Description of component and its importance for CCS as a net zero technology

1.1. Specific

- *Is this specific to the net-zero (NZ) technology?*
 - Yes, post combustion carbon capture technologies are based on liquid solvents, which have been developed and are used specifically for this type of applications. Although solvent based technologies are known in the chemical industry for long time, new generation of solvents dedicated for capturing CO₂ from flue gas sources has been specifically developed for post combustion capture applications.

The reason is that these solvents need to have specific chemical and physical properties related with the application (low degradation in high oxygen and high temperature environments)

- *Components must be either specifically used for this NZ technology or for a limited set of technologies. Is it a component commonly used for a wide variety of products?*
 - Post combustion carbon capture technologies require specialised solvents, which are not used in other applications
- *Is there a specific manufacturing process/facility to produce this component?*
 - Yes, there are dedicated process and facilities for production of these specialised solvents

1.2. Commercially available

- *Is the component mature enough to require manufacturing capacity?*
 - Yes, solvent based carbon capture technology is commercially available at large industrial scale and there are several technology suppliers in the market. An increase of solvent production capacities in Europe may facilitate

1.3. Primarily used

- *Is the component's production output mainly used for the relevant NZ technology?*
 - Yes, post combustion carbon capture technologies require specialised solvents

1.4. Essential

"No easy substitutes"

- *Are there easy substitutes or close substitutes or close technology alternatives?*
 - Although there are different technology options in the market, solvent based technologies are most advanced and mature ones, so they are expected to play a key role, particularly in the short to medium term.

"significant value"

- *Is the component's share of the final product's value significant?*
 - The solvent has a considerable share in operating expenditures of carbon capture units. Without sufficient supply of solvent or sorbent material the CO₂ capture process cannot occur.

2. CO₂ purification and liquefaction equipment

Description of component and its importance for CCS as a net zero technology

2.1. Specific

- *Is this specific to the net-zero (NZ) technology?*
 - CO₂ purification and liquefaction equipment are designed specifically to treat for impurities from flue gases with the specific intention of separating and purifying CO₂ while liquefaction equipment is designed to liquify CO₂ specifically.
- *Components must be either specifically used for this NZ technology or for a limited set of technologies. Is it a component commonly used for a wide variety of products?*
 - While purification and liquefaction equipment can be used for other gases, in cases where CO₂ is the application, they are designed specifically for this purpose
- *Is there a specific manufacturing process/facility to produce this component?*
 - CO₂ purification and liquefaction facilities are purpose-built and components are custom-made

2.2. Commercially available

- *Is the component mature enough to require manufacturing capacity?*
 - CO₂ purification and liquefaction equipment are mature components. With the expansion of CCS projects, additional supply will be required to meet the demands of decarbonisation.

2.3. Primarily used

- *Is the component's production output mainly used for the relevant NZ technology?*
 - CO₂ purification and liquefaction equipment are designed specifically for CCS projects and the output in these cases is especially relevant for CCS.

2.4. Essential

"No easy substitutes"

- *Are there easy substitutes or close substitutes or close technology alternatives?*
 - While various types of CO₂ purification and liquefaction providers exist, the components required for CO₂ purification and liquefaction have no substitutes.

"significant value"

- *Is the component's share of the final product's value significant?*

- CO₂ purification is an essential part of the value chain for all CCS projects. CO₂ liquefaction is an essential part of the value chain for many projects, particularly those where CO₂ is to be shipped, which is the case for dozens of CCS projects in Europe.

3. CO₂ Compressors

Description of component and its importance for CCS as a net zero technology

3.1. Specific

- *Is this specific to the net-zero (NZ) technology?*
 - Although compressors are used in various sectors, CO₂ compressors are designed specifically for the purpose of compressing CO₂ gas.
- *Components must be either specifically used for this NZ technology or for a limited set of technologies. Is it a component commonly used for a wide variety of products?*
 - Compressors are used for the compression of gases. In the energy sector, this includes a limited number of gases including, for example, CO₂, methane, hydrogen and ammonia.
- *Is there a specific manufacturing process/facility to produce this component?*
 - Yes, compressors are manufactured at a production facility with a specific process to design for CO₂ applications.

3.2. Commercially available

- *Is the component mature enough to require manufacturing capacity?*
 - Compressors are a mature technology. With the expansion of CCS projects in Europe, there is a need for additional manufacturing capacity to meet the additional demand.

3.3. Primarily used

- *Is the component's production output mainly used for the relevant NZ technology?*
 - The output of CO₂ compressors is compressed CO₂ gas which is essential for the transport of CO₂ to storage sites from capture plants.

3.4. Essential

“No easy substitutes”

- *Are there easy substitutes or close substitutes or close technology alternatives?*
 - There are no easy substitutes for CO₂ compressors.

“significant value”

- *Is the component's share of the final product's value significant?*
 - Compressors are essential for emitters to transport captured CO₂ gas.

4. CO₂ well drilling equipment

Description of component and its importance for CCS as a net zero technology

4.1. Specific

- *Is this specific to the net-zero (NZ) technology?*
 - No. Such equipment is used globally for geothermal as well as hydrocarbon subsurface drilling.
- *Components must be either specifically used for this NZ technology or for a limited set of technologies. Is it a component commonly used for a wide variety of products?*
 - Certain elements of the well drilling and monitoring equipment are designed and used only for CO₂ wells. Others are designed and used for geothermal and oil & gas exploration and production
- *Is there a specific manufacturing process/facility to produce this component?*
 - These are manufactured globally.

4.2. Commercially available

- *Is the component mature enough to require manufacturing capacity?*
 - Yes. CO₂ well drilling equipment is commercialised and mature, and is manufactured today.

4.3. Primarily used

- *Is the component's production output mainly used for the relevant NZ technology?*
 - Yes. CO₂ specific equipment is used for the creation and monitoring of CO₂ wells. Other equipment is used across CCS, oil & gas, and geothermal projects.

4.4. Essential

"No easy substitutes"

- *Are there easy substitutes or close substitutes or close technology alternatives?*
 - No. Drilling equipment is specific to the industry and there are no substitutes.

"significant value"

- *Is the component's share of the final product's value significant?*
 - Yes. Drilling equipment has a significant value and its sale or rental is a large part of the project cost for drilling CO₂ wells.

5. CO₂ injection wellhead

Description of component and its importance for CCS as a net zero technology

5.1. Specific

- *Is this specific to the net-zero (NZ) technology?*
 - Yes, this type of wellhead will be used specifically for CCS technology. The very challenging condition to operate with CO₂ requires the dedicated wellhead. Wellheads for CO₂ use are created with different materials and specifications (e.g. lower temperature requirements)
- *Components must be either specifically used for this NZ technology or for a limited set of technologies. Is it a component commonly used for a wide variety of products?*
 - Wellhead is a type of product, that is commonly used for oil and gas fields. It is a component at the surface of an oil or gas well that provides the structural and pressure-containing interface for the drilling and production equipment. However, the specific type of wellheads depends on the type of gas used, and even pressure causing significant differences in their construction.
- *Is there a specific manufacturing process/facility to produce this component?*
 - Yes, each wellhead has different specific manufacturing process because of used different types of materials and configurations of sealing system and valves.

5.2. Commercially available

- *Is the component mature enough to require manufacturing capacity?*
 - Injection wellheads are commercially mature but should be designed specifically for each case because of the storage site condition and the CO₂ specification.

5.3. Primarily used

- *Is the component's production output mainly used for the relevant NZ technology?*
 - Yes, CO₂ specific equipment is used for CO₂ wells. Though wellheads are used commonly in the oil and gas and geothermal industry the wellheads for CO₂ injection have to be designed to meet CO₂ environment and very restricted safety requirements.

5.4. Essential

"No easy substitutes"

- *Are there easy substitutes or close substitutes or close technology alternatives?*
 - No, it is one and only dedicated technology for an underground CO₂ storage sites. It is a mandatory equipment to safely inject and store CO₂. Wellheads are very specific to geology, geography, surface or subsea, and the temperature and flow conditions, and there are now similar components.

“significant value”

- *Is the component's share of the final product's value significant?*

Yes. A CO₂ wellhead will be an integrated part of the surface infrastructure on sequestration site. It is impossible to storage gas underground without this component. It provides the possibility to inject, control, measure and safely store CO₂ in the geological formation. It will also be used to conduct the well operation e.g. maintenance works. A wellhead is a significant proportion of a CO₂ well setup cost.

IWG9 COUNTRIES MEETING

1 March 2024, 10:00-11:00 (CET)

DRAFT AGENDA

Item	Lead Presenter	Time
1. Welcome and introduction	IWG9 co-chairs	10:00-10:10
2. Policy developments	IWG9/ZEP secretariat, DG RTD	10:10-10:25
3. Way forward for the IWG9	IWG9 co-chairs, Marie Bysveen, DG RTD	10:25-10:55
4. Closing remarks	IWG9 co-chairs	10:55-11:00

WELCOME AND INTRODUCTION

- **CCUS SET-Plan Implementation Plan (IWG9)** chaired by the Netherlands, Norway, and the Zero Emissions Platform
- **Accelerating the transition through greater coordination** – EU, national, industrial and academic research
- **All parts of CCUS value chain**, including low-carbon hydrogen and CDR
- Updated CCUS targets: **50 MtCO₂/yr abated by CCS in 2030**

WELCOME AND INTRODUCTION

50 Mtpa abated by CCS in 2030

WELCOME AND INTRODUCTION

- The 2020s will be crucial for the development of CCS and CCU – urgency to deploy at scale
- **CCUS Roadmap to 2030 – actions needed for a large-scale development and deployment of CCS and CCU in the 2020s and to be on track for climate-neutrality**
 - Role of CCS and CCU for a just cost-efficient transition
 - Status and progress today
 - Technical development and deployment of CCS and CCU
 - Policy frameworks, business models, R&D&I...

POLICY DEVELOPMENTS

EU policy developments for CCS/CCU

- Very active policy period
- Proposed EU 2040 climate target published on 6 February
- Industrial carbon management strategy published on 6 February
- Net Zero Industry Act expected to enter into force in July

POLICY DEVELOPMENTS

New targets/modelling figures – Net Zero Industry Act and EU strategy

- 50 million tonnes of CO₂ captured and stored annually by 2030 in the EU
- 280 tonnes of CO₂ captured annually by 2040 in the EU
- 450 tonnes of CO₂ captured annually by 2050 in the EU
- 250 tonnes of CO₂ as minimum annual injection capacity in 2040 in the EEA

New targets/modelling figures – proposed EU climate target for 2040

- 137 million tonnes of CO₂ captured from industrial processes by 2040 in the EU
- 32 tonnes of CO₂ captured from industrial processes by 2040 in the EU
- 101 tonnes of CO₂ used for e-fuels annually by 2040 in the EU

POLICY DEVELOPMENTS

Net Zero Industry Act – geological data

- geological services in the EEA should be resourced and able to **aggregate** all existing **subsoil knowledge**
- this should include **technical information** such as well samples, geophysical behaviour, seismic data from hydrocarbon production sites and early CO2 storage sites
- **investors** should be able to use this atlas to identify potential storage opportunities as part of CO2 value chains

POLICY DEVELOPMENTS

Creation of the SET Plan Steering Group under the Net Zero Industry Act

- *“since its beginning in 2007, the SET Plan was an **unofficial** forum”*
- *“structuring effect on joint Research and Innovation (R&I) actions, helping them deliver on common energy research and technology objectives with **greater speed and effectiveness**”*
- *“helped **aligning** the R&I efforts and **leverage national public funding** of participating countries to support jointly agreed R&I priorities through the Clean Energy Transition Partnership and the Driving Urban Transition Partnership under Horizon Europe, as an example of successful EU cross-sectoral cooperation”*

POLICY DEVELOPMENTS

Article 27a

Establishment of the Strategic Energy Technology (SET) Plan Steering Group

1. *The SET Plan Steering Group is hereby established;*
2. *The SET Plan Steering Group shall perform the tasks entrusted to it in this Regulation.*

Article 27b

Tasks of the SET Plan Steering Group

1. *The SET Plan Steering Group shall provide guidance and direction to the Strategic Energy Technology (SET) Plan.*
2. *The Commission and Member States shall work and coordinate within the SET Plan Steering Group to help support the development of clean, efficient and cost-competitive energy technologies through coordination and collaboration in clean energy research and innovation (R&I) and where relevant with third countries upon invitation.*
3. *The SET Plan Steering Group shall advice and assist the Commission in setting up initiatives related to the tasks referred to in paragraph 1 and 2.*

POLICY DEVELOPMENTS

Article 27c

Structure and functioning of the SET Plan Steering Group

- 1. The SET Plan Steering Group shall be composed of EU Member States and the Commission. It shall be chaired by one or more representatives of the Commission.*
- 2. Each Member State shall appoint a high-level representative to the SET Plan Steering Group. Where relevant as regards the function and expertise, a Member State may have more than one representative in relation to different tasks related to the work of the SET Plan Steering Group. Each member of the SET Plan Steering Group shall have an alternate.*
- 3. On a proposal by the Commission, the SET Plan Steering Group shall adopt its rules of procedure by a simple majority of its members.*
- 4. The SET Plan Steering Group shall meet at regular intervals to ensure the effective performance of its tasks. Where necessary, the SET Plan Steering Group shall meet at the reasoned request of the Commission or a simple majority of its members.*
- 5. The Commission shall assist the SET Plan Steering Group by means of an executive secretariat that provides technical and logistic support.*
- 6. The SET Plan Steering Group may establish standing or temporary working groups and task forces dealing with specific questions and tasks.*

POLICY DEVELOPMENTS

Consequences

- legal basis to the SET Plan
- current framework of the SET Plan remains overall unchanged
- higher political involvement of Member States expected
- no change in the way the IWGs have worked so far, nor the nature of the relationship between the IWG and the Steering Group
- expected creation of the task-forces, to include the 5 identified cross-cutting topics (Access to the Market, Circularity & Materials, Digitalisation, R&I for Societal Needs, and Skills)

WAY FORWARD FOR THE IWG9

- Review of the IWG9 R&I targets and activities
- How we operate – plenary and working groups
- Workplan
- How can countries contribute?

WAY FORWARD FOR THE IWG9

SET Plan IWG9 Plenary

IWG9 Strategic Coordination Group

WG1

Full scale projects, clusters
and infrastructure

WG2

CO2 capture

WG3

CO2 storage

WG4

CO2 Use

WAY FORWARD FOR THE IWG9

IWG9 Strategic Coordination Group (SCG)

- Co-chairs: William C., Eve T., Joelle R.,
- WG leads: Stijn, Lamberto, Marie, Filip, Jonathan, Anastasios
- Meeting organisers/secretariat: Charles A., Joop
- Meet 4 times/year, one month ahead of IWG9 Plenary meetings

IWG9 Working Groups

- WG1. Full scale projects, clusters and infra.:
- WG2. CO2 capture : Marie & x
- WG3. CO2 storage: Filip & Jonathan
- WG4. CO2 use: Anastasios & x

(by: ZEP Projects Network)

(by: EERA JP CCS and ZEP Technology Committee)

(by: ZEP Technology Committee and EERA JP CCS)

(by: ZEP Technology Committee)

WG leads organise discussions with stakeholders mainly through existing set-ups like ZEP Technology Committee,

EERA JP CCS and Projects Network

www.ccus-setplan.eu

WAY FORWARD FOR THE IWG9

SET Plan IWG9 planning

Type of meetings/Months	Jan	Febr	March	April	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
IWG9 meetings												
ZEP AC/IWG9 Plenary			X			X			X			X
IWG9 Strategic Co-ordination Group		X			X			X			X	
IWG9 Countries		X						X				
Existing ZEP/EERA networks contributing to IWG9												
EERA JP CCS			X			X						X
ZEP Technical Committee		22.feb			08.mai				25.sep		20.nov	
ZEP Projects Network	X											X

WG1 Full scale projects, clusters and infra (ZEP Projects Network ? TBD)

WG2 CO2 capture (EERA JP CCS and ZEP Technology Committee. Lead: Marie Bysveen, xx. TBD)

WG3 CO2 storage (EERA JP CCS and ZEP Technology Committee. Lead: Filip Neele, Jonathan Pearce, TDB)

WG4. CO2 use (ZEP Technology Committee. Lead: Anastasios Perimenis - TBD)

IWG9 Strategic Coordination Group : IWG9 Co-chairs, IWG9 WG leads, DG RTD, DG ENER (?)

WAY FORWARD FOR THE IWG9

Q1, Q2 2024:

- Draft and finalise new IWG9 targets and R&I actions
- Update at ZEP AC/IWG9 Plenary on 20 March and 19 June 2024

Q3 2024:

- IWG9 work update at ZEP AC/IWG9 Plenary on 11 September 2024

Q4 2024:

- IWG9 work update at ZEP AC/IWG9 Plenary on 4 December 2024

WAY FORWARD FOR THE IWG9

How can countries contribute?

- Countries representatives are invited to join the working groups and contribute to the new R&I activities and targets

CLOSING REMARKS

- Any final remark?

Implementation Working Group 9 meeting

1 March 2023, 10:00-11:00 CET

Draft meeting agenda

Item	Lead Presenter	Time
1 Welcome and introduction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Brief introduction of the SET-plan activities and the IWG 9 on CCUS 	IWG9 co-chairs	10:00-10:10
2 Policy developments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> New policy targets for CCS/CCU under the Net Zero Industry Act and the industrial carbon management strategy Creation of the SET Plan Steering Group under the Net Zero Industry Act 	To be confirmed	10:10-10:25
3 Way forward for the IWG9 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review of the IWG9 R&I targets and activities How we operate – plenary and working groups Workplan How can countries contribute? 	IWG9 co-chairs, Marie Bysveen, DG RTD	10:25-10:55
4 Closing remarks	IWG9 co-chairs	10:55-11:00

SET PLAN STEERING GROUP

ZEP/IWG9 Grant
14 December 2023

SET Plan Steering Group

14 December 2023

Zero Emissions Platform

Website: zeroemissionsplatform.eu
Twitter: @EUCarbonCapture

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement 101075790.

CCUS SET-PLAN – ACCELERATING THE TRANSITION

- **CCUS SET-Plan Implementation Plan (IWG9)** chaired by the Netherlands, Norway, and the Zero Emissions Platform
- **Accelerating the transition through greater coordination** – EU, national, industrial and academic research
- **All parts of CCUS value chain**, including low-carbon hydrogen and CDR
- Updated CCUS targets: **50 MtCO₂/yr abated by CCS in 2030**

CCUS SET PLAN 2030 TARGETS

50 Mtpa abated by CCS in 2030

CCUS ROADMAP 2030

- The 2020s will be crucial for the development of CCS and CCU – urgency to deploy at scale
- **CCUS Roadmap to 2030 – actions needed for a large-scale development and deployment of CCS and CCU in the 2020s and to be on track for climate-neutrality**
 - Role of CCS and CCU for a just cost-efficient transition
 - Status and progress today
 - Technical development and deployment of CCS and CCU
 - Policy frameworks, business models, R&D&I...

SET PLAN IWG9 WORK 2024

1. Review IWG9 targets
2. Review IWG9 R&I actions, and possibly a Strategic Research Agenda (SRIA)
3. Facilitate stakeholders to contribute – including, Governments, ZEP, IWG9 and EERA

DRAFT WORK PLAN 2024

Q1, Q2 2024: Draft and finalise new IWG9 targets and R&I actions. Update at ZEP AC/IWG9 Plenary on 20 March and 19 June 2024

Q3 2024: IWG9 work update at ZEP AC/IWG9 Plenary on 11 September 2024

Q4 2024: IWG9 work update at ZEP AC/IWG9 Plenary on 4 December 2024

Coordinating the Zero Emissions Platform and the SET-Plan Implementation Plan WG

Effective cooperation between stakeholders – support the SET Plan Implementation Plan

Preserving the IWG9 and ZEP strengths and coordinating activities to increase efficiency

- “Open board meetings” – ZEP Advisory Council and IWG9 Plenary
- Government Group
- Policy & Economics and Technology Committee
- Projects Network
- External Relations Committee

Zero Emissions Platform – *who we are*

Zero Emissions Platform (ZEP) – European Technology and Innovation Platform (ETIP) under the SET Plan

EU advisory body on CCS and CCU deployment and development

ZEP unites a **diverse range of stakeholders** from oil and gas companies, hard-to-abate industries, researchers and environmental NGOs

Objective: create the conditions to reach net-zero by 2050 Demonstrate that CCS and CCU is essential for this goal

- 1 Create the right conditions to reach net-zero by 2050 focusing on energy and industrial sectors.
- 2 Demonstrate that the implementation of CCS and some applications of CCU technologies are essential to this goal.
- 3 Accelerate the deployment of large-scale CO₂ transport and storage networks.

How to make it possible?

Development of European CO2 transport and storage infrastructure

An enabling policy framework making it economically feasible to invest in CCS and CCU

Incentives to support large-scale deployment of all parts along the CCS and CCU value chain

Strong continued support for CCS and CCU Research and Innovation

Zero Emissions Platform – impact

Policy work

- Net Zero Industry Act
- EU carbon removal certification framework
- Industrial carbon management strategy
- National energy and climate plans

Technical reports

- ‘Experience in developing CO₂ storage under the CO₂ storage directive’ and others...
- *January 2024: ‘Achieving a European market for CO₂ transport by ship’*

CCS and CCU projects in Europe - latest

More than 70 market-ready CCS and CCU projects looking to become operational by 2030

Northern Light project in Norway to start operations in 2024

Porthos CCS project took FID, operational by 2026

2023 – a pivotal year for CCS

2023

→ March 2023 – Net Zero Industry Act

- Focus on CO2 injection capacity
- Objective of **50 Mtpa CO2 injection capacity by 2030**
- Member States to build up capacity:
Reporting on storage and project progress
- Faster permitting – up to 18 months, less administrative burden.
- Ongoing trilogues – expected to be adopted in 2024

→ June 2023 - National Energy and Climate Plans

- EU Member States strategy to achieve nationally determined climate targets
- Expecting Poland, Latvia...
- Member States encouraged to cover CCS in the updated plans

More to come in 2024...

2024

→ Certification of Carbon Removals – Q1 2024?

- Ongoing trilogues
- ZEP active in the Carbon Removal Expert Group

→ Revision of the monitoring and reporting regulation – 2024

- Revision of the EU ETS directive
- Delegated acts on permanent CCU and CO2 transport

→ EU Industrial Carbon Management Strategy – Q1 2024

- Dedicated regulatory framework for CO2 transport and storage
- CCUS Forum WGs – ZEP co-chairs WG on CO2 infrastructure
- CCUS Forum in Denmark 27-28 November – to guide the strategy

→ Proposal for a 2040 target – Q1 2024

- Impactful for CCS deployment targets

Net Zero Industry Act – a closer look

- **Objective for CO2 storage capacity** of at least 50 Mtpa by 2030
- **Oil and gas producers to contribute** via pro rata obligation
- **Member States (MS) to report**
 - where CO2 storage sites can be permitted – oil & gas licence holders to report geological data
 - on capture and storage projects progress
- MS to support strategic projects **on access to finance**, administrative procedures, and public acceptance
- Regional and local authorities to include CO2 storage projects in **zoning, spatial, and land use plans**
- **Permit process maximum 18 months** for CO2 storage projects and manufacturing of components
- **Member States to build up competent authorities' resources on CO2 storage**
- **Net-Zero Europe Platform:** assist the EC and MS on implementation of the proposed regulation and support knowledge sharing
- **Net-Zero Industry Academies:** develop/deploy education and training

Key developments (1/2)

- 14 projects selected for PCI/PMI status
- Northern Lights, Nautilus, Pycasso, Prinos, Norne, GT CCS Croatia, EU2NSEA, Delta Rhine Corridor, CCS Baltic Consortium, Callisto, Bifrost, ECO2CEE, Aramis, Porthos
- UK in Norne (emitters) and ECO2CEE (storage)
- Standardisation work on CCS and CCU will be initiated
- New CCS Observatory to monitor, report, and verify the CO₂ captured from cement and waste incineration plants
- New industrial carbon management knowledge sharing network for CCS projects

Key developments (2/2)

- Aalborg Declaration signed by Denmark, France, Germany, Sweden, and the Netherlands:
- “welcome CCS as a climate tool and do not condone the use of CCS to increase fossil fuel extraction and production”
- “strive for a European unified CCS and CCU market”
- “for CCUS to be an efficient climate tool, a full value chain approach is needed”

Connecting Europe Facility – Energy

- Close to €480 million of CEF funding awarded to 4 CO₂ transport and storage projects
- **D'Artagnan**: Maximum of €189 million for a collecting pipeline and an export terminal
- **CO₂NEXT**: €33 million for an import terminal at the Port of Rotterdam
- **Aramis**: €124 million for a 200 km undersea trunkline
- **Northern Lights**: €131 million for the expansion of the CO₂ import terminal and offshore pipeline to the storage site
- €2.54 million to **EU CCS Interconnector** (Gdansk) for studies

Thank you!
Any question?